

Table S3. NRM and SIRM data of Australasian tektites from South China.

Sample ID	Type	NRM (Am ² /kg)	SIRM (Am ² /kg)	NRM/SIRM ratio
HN6-2S	Muong Nong-type	1.41E-05	2.41E-04	0.058
HN6-1	Muong Nong-type	1.36E-05		
HN9	Muong Nong-type	8.40E-06	7.03E-05	0.120
HN-4	Muong Nong-type	4.38E-06		
HN4S	Muong Nong-type	4.19E-06	1.91E-05	0.220
MNKS	Muong Nong-type	2.40E-06	8.66E-05	0.028
MNK-4	Muong Nong-type	1.80E-06		
HN2-1	Muong Nong-type	1.32E-06		
HN7-3	Muong Nong-type	1.18E-06		
HN2-1S	Muong Nong-type	1.13E-06	5.37E-05	0.021
HN1-2S	Muong Nong-type	1.03E-06	6.00E-06	0.172
MNL-1	Muong Nong-type	8.55E-07		
HN2-2	Muong Nong-type	8.44E-07		
HN5-1	Muong Nong-type	8.17E-07		
MNL-1S	Muong Nong-type	8.09E-07	4.70E-05	0.017
HN5-2	Muong Nong-type	7.53E-07		
MNL-2	Muong Nong-type	7.43E-07		
HN5S	Muong Nong-type	4.82E-07	1.63E-05	0.030
HN8	Muong Nong-type	3.84E-07	2.44E-05	0.016
HN7-4	Muong Nong-type	3.08E-07		
HN1-2	Muong Nong-type	2.40E-07		
HN7S	Muong Nong-type	1.58E-07	9.51E-06	0.017
HN1-1	Muong Nong-type	1.56E-07		
HN-3	Muong Nong-type	8.31E-08		
HN3S	Muong Nong-type	8.31E-08	1.05E-05	0.008
HNWC-2	Splash-form	1.00E-07		
ZJDT-2-3	Splash-form	9.21E-08	4.12E-06	0.022
GDWC-T1	Splash-form	5.26E-08	7.62E-06	0.007
ZJZW-1	Splash-form	4.72E-08	1.36E-05	0.003
GDZJ-S5-1	Splash-form	4.01E-08		
GXYL-S3	Splash-form	3.87E-08		
ZJDT-2-1	Splash-form	2.54E-08	1.63E-06	0.016

ZJZW-2	Splash-form	2.53E-08	1.67E-06	0.015
HNWC-1	Splash-form	2.48E-08		
GDLZ-S2	Splash-form	2.15E-08		
HNHK-S1	Splash-form	1.78E-08	1.94E-06	0.009
MMX-1	Splash-form	1.54E-08	2.56E-06	0.006
ZWC-9-2S	Splash-form	1.50E-08	5.34E-07	0.028
GDZJ-S5-2	Splash-form	1.49E-08		
GDLZ-5	Splash-form	1.40E-08	2.18E-06	0.006
GXYL-3-2	Splash-form	1.26E-08	1.73E-06	0.007
GDWC-D1	Splash-form	1.21E-08	7.26E-07	0.017
GDWC-T2	Splash-form	1.19E-08	8.30E-07	0.014
GDWC-D2	Splash-form	1.17E-08	2.45E-06	0.005
GDMM-2-1	Splash-form	1.15E-08	1.16E-06	0.010
WSD-1-1	Splash-form	1.10E-08		
WSD-R2	Splash-form	1.01E-08	2.73E-06	0.004
GDZJ-S6	Splash-form	9.97E-09	1.26E-06	0.008
GDMM-2-3	Splash-form	9.77E-09	2.67E-06	0.004
GDLZ-S4B2	Splash-form	9.73E-09	1.19E-06	0.008
GPZ-1	Splash-form	8.78E-09		
GXYL-2-2	Splash-form	8.69E-09	1.56E-06	0.006
GDLZ-2	Splash-form	8.56E-09	6.76E-07	0.013
HNHKS1E-3S	Splash-form	8.35E-09	6.48E-07	0.013
GDLZ-S4B1	Splash-form	7.95E-09	4.15E-07	0.019
GXYL-2-1	Splash-form	7.75E-09	1.06E-06	0.007
LZS2-R1	Splash-form	7.56E-09	1.47E-06	0.005
WSD-1-2	Splash-form	7.10E-09		
BSP	Splash-form	6.39E-09	9.25E-07	0.007
HNWC-1-2	Splash-form	6.27E-09	1.88E-06	0.003
ZWC-9-2	Splash-form	5.80E-09		
ZWC-9-1	Splash-form	5.76E-09		
GDWC-2-3	Splash-form	5.74E-09	1.54E-06	0.004
GDZJ-S4-1	Splash-form	5.59E-09	6.45E-07	0.009
HKS1E-2	Splash-form	5.09E-09		
GDWC-S1-2	Splash-form	4.90E-09	4.71E-07	0.010
GC-1	Splash-form	4.82E-09	1.51E-06	0.003
WSD-3	Splash-form	4.81E-09	7.14E-07	0.007

HKS1E-3	Splash-form	4.36E-09		
EC-2	Splash-form	3.92E-09	1.87E-06	0.002
GDWC-1	Splash-form	3.65E-09	1.61E-06	0.002
LZS2-R2	Splash-form	2.68E-09	1.26E-06	0.002
GDZJ-S5	Splash-form	2.27E-09		
GDZJ-S3	Splash-form	1.52E-09		